

Reaction of Lithium Aluminum Hydride with Methylenebenzanthrene

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The relatively stable benzenoid odd-alternant ions formed by attack of hydride from LiAlH_4 at the exocyclic carbon accounts for the unusual reactivity of methylenebenzanthrene. The enhanced reactivity of methylenebenzanthrene is reflected in HMO calculations: atom-atom polarizabilities of the exocyclic carbon atoms are unusually high, and localization energies are quite low compared to other aryl olefins. We report here the first instance of a facile reaction of LiAlH_4 with an alternant hydrocarbon, namely the conversion of methylenebenzanthrene to 7-methylbenzanthrenyl lithium.

It has been known for some time that fulvenes and fulvalenes, hydrocarbons with non-uniform charge distributions, react readily with lithium aluminum hydride, whereas alternant aromatic olefins, such as 1,1-diphenylethylene, do not^{1,2}. The various benzanthrenes are unstable to light and oxygen, as is phenalene.

Experimental

Preparation of 7-Methylbenzanthren-7-ol II

Benzanthrone I (10 g) was dissolved in 200 ml of dry ether in a three-necked flask. An excess (100 ml) of methyl lithium was added by means of a hypodermic syringe. The reaction mixture was stirred overnight at room temperature under nitrogen atmosphere. The lithium salt of the alcohol was hydrolysed by dropwise addition of 100 ml water by dropping funnel. The alcohol was extracted with ether and combined ether extracts were dried over anhydrous magnesium sulfate. Evaporation of ether yielded 9 g (80%) of alcohol which was purified by recrystallization from carbon tetrachloride. The alcohol has melting point of 144.5°. Carbon hydrogen analyses, Calculated: C, 87.80%; H, 5.60%. Found: C, 87.89%; H, 6.61%.

Preparation of Methylenebenzanthrene III

7-Methylbenzanthren-7-ol II (5 g) was dissolved in 250 ml dry ether in a three-necked flask. 100 ml of 10% sulfuric acid was added to the flask to dehydrate the alcohol. The reaction mixture was stirred overnight and the precipitated solid was filtered and washed with water to ensure complete removal of sulfuric acid. The dried compound weighed 4.5 g (90%). It was recrystallized from carbon tetrachloride and absolute alcohol. The melting point of the compound is 164°-165°. Elemental analyses, Calculated: C, 94.74%; H, 5.26%. Found: C, 94.73%; H, 5.28%.

Preparation of 7-Methylbenzanthren-3-one IV

Lithium aluminum hydride (2 g) was suspended in 50 ml tetrahydrofuran in three-necked flask under inert nitrogen atmosphere. Methylenebenzanthrene (5 g) was dissolved in tetrahydrofuran and was added slowly by dropping funnel. The reaction was vigorous and red color was developed immediately indicating the formation of 7-methylbenzanthrenyl anion. After one hour absolute alcohol was added drop by drop through dropping funnel to destroy excess LiAlH_4 and to destroy lithium derivative of methylenebenzanthrene. The solution was poured into a beaker and kept overnight to evaporate THF and alcohol. The compound was extracted with dry ether and the combined ether extracts were dried over magnesium sulfate. It was filtered and the ether was stripped off from the filtrate leaving the crude solid 0.5 g (84% yield). It was purified by recrystallization from absolute alcohol. The melting point of the ketone IV is 161°-162° and is uncorrected. Elemental analyses, Calculated: C, 88.52%; H, 4.92%. Found: C, 88.49%; H, 4.98%.

Discussion

Methylenebenzanthrene III was synthesized by acid-catalyzed dehydration of 7-methylbenzanthren-7-ol II which in turn prepared by the reaction of benzanthrone I with methyl lithium. (Fig. 1). Chemical confirmation of the structure III was provided by ozonolysis from which benzanthrone I was isolated.

Fig. 1. Preparation of Methylenebenzanthrene.

When the solution of methylenebenzanthrene III in tetrahydrofuran was added to the suspension of LiAlH_4 in the same solvent under nitrogen at room

temperature, the deep red colored 7-methylbenzanthrenyl lithium is formed. Quenching the reaction with ethanol and extraction with ether affords a ketone which is most likely 7-methylbenzanthren-3-one IV (Fig. 2). The various benzanthrenes are unstable to light and oxygen as is phenalene. Our

Fig. 2. Reaction Mechanism for 7-Methylbenzanthrene-3-one.

tentative assignment of the carbonyl to the 3 position is based on the work of H. Dannenberg and H. J. Kessler^{3,4}. The ketone IV shows a strong Infrared absorption at 1635 cm^{-1} (Phenalenone displays its carbonyl stretching band⁵ at 1637 cm^{-1}) as well as NMR signals in CCl_4 at $\delta 7.5$ center of complex multiplet and $\delta 2.1$ singlet, area ratio 3 : 1. The elemental analyses of the new compound agree with calculation and its infrared and NMR spectra are consistent with assigned structure.

Correlation

The relatively stable benzenoid odd-alternant ions formed by attack of hydride from LiAlH_4 at the exocyclic carbon accounts for the unusual reactivity of methylenebenzanthrene. Methylenebenzanthrene is a member of a group of cross-conjugated exocyclic olefins of which the simplest member is the extremely reactive para-xylylene⁶ for which we suggest the name benzenogenic. The enhanced reactivity of benzenogenic olefins is reflected in HMO calculations : atom-atom polarizabilities of the exocyclic carbon

atoms are unusually high, and localization energies (π -electron energy difference between olefin and ion)

TABLE I

Olefin	ΔE_{π^a}	$\pi r, r^b$	Forms RLi with LiAlH_4
Fulvalene (1-Position)	0.84		Yes
Fulvene	0.99		Yes
Benzofulvene	1.16		
Para-Xylylene	1.20	0.98	
Methylenephenalene	1.26	0.90	
Methylenefluorene	1.31		Yes
Methylenebenzanthrene	1.33	0.78	Yes
1,1-diphenylethylene	1.51	0.69	No
Styrene	1.70	0.60	No

a. Localization energies. HMO calculated difference between π -energy of olefin and carbanion formed by hydride addition to the exocyclic carbon, neglecting methyl groups in the ion.

b. Atom-atom polarizability for exocyclic carbon. Calculations derived from A. Streitwieser, Jr. and J. I. Brauman, "Supplemental Tables of Molecular Orbital Calculations", Pergamon, Oxford, 1965.

are quite low compared to other aryl olefins. Calculations for some representative olefins are given in Table I.

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